
CAPSAICINOIDS CONTENT IN FOUR TUNISIAN HOT PEPPER VARIETIES GROWN IN AN OPEN FIELD (*Capsicum annuum* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Quantitative analysis of capsaicinoids in various parts of the fruits (pericarp, placenta and seeds) of four hot peppers varieties, cultivated in Tunisia *Capsicum annuum* L. were determined by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). Total capsaicinoids content varied according to the variety, and within the same variety according to the stage of maturity and different parts of the fruit. Capsaicinoids content was higher in the placenta than in other parts, but lowest in seeds as well as in green and red fruit. 'Piment Sesseb' and 'Rouge Long' varieties had the highest total capsaicinoids contents in green and red pepper fruit but "Baklouti Kairouan" had the lowest. In each of peppers studied, the placenta had the highest capsaicinoids content, followed by the pericarp, the seeds had the lowest. The capsaicinoids content in the placenta ranged from $3.06 \pm 0.046 \text{ mg.g}^{-1}$ to $0.28 \pm 0.002 \text{ mg.g}^{-1}$ in the green pepper "Piment Sesseb" and "Baklouti Kairouan" respectively. The content in the seeds was ranged from $0.27 \pm 0.0008 \text{ mg.g}^{-1}$ to $0.04 \pm 0.0008 \text{ mg.g}^{-1}$ dry weight in the same varieties respectively. In the red pepper fruits, capsaicinoids content in the placenta ranged from 2.32 ± 0.058 to $0.065 \pm 0.011 \text{ mg.g}^{-1}$ in the "Piment Sesseb" and "Baklouti Kairouan" respectively. The content in the seeds was ranged from $0.17 \pm 0.016 \text{ mg.g}^{-1}$ to $0.005 \pm 0.00018 \text{ mg.g}^{-1}$ dry weight in the same varieties respectively. Capsaicinoids content was higher in green pepper fruits than in red ones for various parts of the fruit.

KEYWORDS: Hot Pepper, Capsaicinoids, High Performance Liquid Chromatography

INTRODUCTION

Pepper is an important agricultural crop, not only because of its economic importance, but also for the nutritional value of its fruits, mainly due to the fact that they are an excellent source of natural colors and antioxidant compounds (Nevarro *et al.*, 2006).

Peppers are classified by fruit characteristics, i.e. pungency, color, shape, flavor, size, and their use (Smith *et al.* 1987; Bosland 1992). Hot peppers are popular food in many parts of the world for their sensory attributes pungency and aroma. Most parts of the world, pungency increases the acceptance of the insipid basic nutrient foods (Bosland 1999). In Tunisia Hot peppers (*Capsicum annuum* L.) are widely produced and consumed as raw, cooked, or processed products. The consumption of hot peppers is due mainly to their very pungent flavor. Pungency is a key characteristic associated with members of the genus *Capsicum* and is also an important fruit quality attribute (Jarret *et al.*, 2007). The pungency is caused by capsaicinoids, and among the most abundant of these components are capsaicin (trans-8 methyl-N-vanillyl-6-nonenamide) and dihydrocapsaicin (8 methyl-Nvanillylnonanamide), which are responsible for about 90% of total pungency (Ravishankar *et al.* 2003; De Masi *et al.*, 2007). In addition to capsaicin and dihydrocapsaicin, many less abundant capsaicinoids have been detected in *Capsicum* extracts, including nordihydrocapsaicin, norcapsaicin, homocapsaicin, homodihydrocapsaicin, etc. (Constant & Cordell, 1996, 1995). An accurate determination of the levels of various capsaicinoids has become important because of the increasing demand by consumers for spicy foods, and the increasing use in pharmaceuticals (Kaale *et al.*, 2002).

In addition to being widely utilized to give a peppery flavor to meals, capsaicinoids are molecules that have various other properties and applications that make these compounds very interesting to study. All of these capsaicinoids have a notable antimutagenic and antitumoral property (Surh *et al.*, 1995; Surh and Seoul, 2002; Antonius *et al.*, 2009) they also present a high antioxidant activity (Henderson & Slickman, 1999; Antonius *et al.*, 2009).

The first reported reliable measurement of chile pungency is the Scoville organoleptic test (Collins *et al.*, 1995). However this test is subjective and has been replaced with a variety of methods such as High performance Liquid chromatography (HPLC) methods which are considered more reliable and accurate.

The literature contains little information on variability in capsaicinoids content among varieties of genre capsicum in Tunisia. This study was undertaken to examine varieties of hot pepper fruits of *C. annum* for variability in fruit concentrations of capsaicinoids that might subsequently be utilized to enhance fruit content of capsaicinoids.

The aim of this work was to employ the use of a simple method to extract and determine the capsaicinoids content in the various parts of some peppers grown in Tunisia using HPLC with a view to establishing the part with highest content. This work also seeks to carry-out the effect of maturity staid on capsaicinoids content in the fruits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

Four local hot pepper varieties were used as representative landraces of two regions, Kairouan and Sahel: 'Rouge Long', 'Chaabani', 'Baklouti Kairouan' and 'Piment de Sesseb'. Seeds of those materials were sown in alveolar containers and containing fertilized peat (nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, N-P-K, 12-14-24). When the 6-8th leaves emerged, 40 plants were transplanted on April, 2005, to on open field at a density of 3 plants/m² after soil fertilization with N, P and K according to Chau and Foury (1994). The experiment was a completely randomized design with four replications of each treatment/plot. Only a single season was assessed.

Capsaicinoid analysis

Simultaneously, 10 mature fruits (collected for each variety) were harvested at the green and red stages. In separate samples also with 10 fruits, we extracted the placenta, the seeds and the pericarp from green and red mature fruits for every accession. All parts of the fruit were oven-dried at 60°C until constant weight (2 to 3 days) and then ground by a mini- grinder for capsaicinoid analysis. Capsaicinoids were extracted and analyzed by HPLC (Hewlett Packard Ti-series 1050) according to the method of Collins *et al.* (1995) with some modification as indicated next. 2 g of each pepper sample ground was mixed with 20 ml of acetonitrile and kept for 4 h at 80°C in a water bath with constant shaking and without reflux. Then, after cooling, the supernatant of each extract was further filtered through a 0.45 µm nylon filter before the HPLC analysis. A waters HPLC (Hewlett Packard Ti-series 1050) equipped with a Nova-pack C18 reverse phase column ODS of 4 × 250 mm was used. The mobile phase was isocratic, methanol/water at a ratio of 82:18, and the flow rate was 0.7 ml/min and run for a total of 10 min. The HPLC instrument was equipped with fluorescence detectors at 280 nm excitation and emission at 338 nm. 5 µl of any filtrate was injected at the HPLC in order to determine the total capsaicinoids content in every part of pepper fruit. The procedure was repeated three times for each sample; data was presented as means ± standard errors.

Standard Curve

Standards of capsaicin and dihydrocapsaicin were obtained from Sigma Chemical Co. (St Louis, MO) and were used for verification of retention-time and instrument calibration. Quantifications were based on average peak areas of 5 µL injections obtained from external standard solutions of capsaicinoids prepared in methanol. Under these conditions, retention times were 4.58 and 5.21 min for capsaicin and dihydrocapsaicin, respectively (Fig1). Peak identities were confirmed by consistent retention time and co-elution with standards under the conditions described above. Quantification of capsaicinoids of different part of varieties was performed according to Collins *et al.* (1995).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Extraction and quantitation was carried-out in triplicate for each variety. The standards used for the standard curve were injected at intervals during sample injection to confirm retention time.

Fig1 : Chromatogram of a mixture of capsaicin and dihydrocapsaicin standards.

Capsaicinoids in different parts of the pepper fruit

Figure 2 and 3 shows the distribution of capsaicinoids in placenta, pericarp and seeds of hot Tunisian pepper varieties in green and red fruits. The total capsaicinoids in dry mature fruits for all varieties differed according to the stage of maturity and part of the fruit. High total capsaicinoids content was observed in ‘Piment Sesseb’ and ‘Rouge Long’; ‘Baklouti Kairouan’ had the lowest content for the red and green fruits. The content of total capsaicinoids in green fruits ranged from 3.06 mg.g⁻¹ to 0.28 mg.g⁻¹ in placenta of piment Sesseb and Baklouti Kairouan respectively; in seeds ranged from 0.28 mg.g⁻¹ to 0.03 mg.g⁻¹ of dry weight of piment Sesseb and Chaabani respectively. Whereas capsaicinoides level in the red berries of pepper is ranged from 2.32 mg.g⁻¹ to 0.065 mg.g⁻¹ in placenta parts of of piment Sesseb and Baklouti Kairouan respectively. The corresponding amount in the seeds was ranged from 0.17 mg.g⁻¹ to 0.005 mg.g⁻¹ dry weight in the same varieties respectively.

Variability in the level of capsaicinoids has been reported by many authors working on hot pepper and under the same conditions (i.e., open field production). Our findings are in agreement with those of Choi *et al.* (2006) who found 3.53 mg.g⁻¹ dry weight (DW) for whole dry pepper fruit (chili powder) and 0.43 mg.g⁻¹ DW for red pepper powder and Estrada *et al.* (2002) who showed that the variation of capsaicinoids content in 11 red pepper varieties ranged from 0.78 mg.g⁻¹ dry weight (DW) to 1.09 mg.g⁻¹ DW for the basal fruit and the apical fruit, respectively. De Masi *et al.* (2007), using eight pepper varieties, found the capsaicinoids content to range from 0.66 to 3.69 mg.g⁻¹ for dry weight (DW) fruit. Among fresh peppers, Kosukue *et al.* (2005) found in the different part of the hot pepper variety “Seongrok” 1.85 mg.g⁻¹ fresh weight in placenta, 0.18 mg.g⁻¹ in pericarp and 0.14 mg.g⁻¹ in seeds. Moreover, Canto-flick *et al.* (2008) show a considerable variation in the capsaicinoid content not only among the parts of the fruit, but also among the fruit from different accessions.

Capsaicinoids content also differed significantly in different parts of green fruits, highest in the placenta, lowest in seeds for both green and red parts. It clearly follows from the results shown in Table1 and Table2, that the distribution of capsaicinoids in the pepper fruit is varied and uneven. In each of the pepper varieties used in this study, the placenta had the highest capsaicin concentration followed by the pericarp, whereas the seeds had the lowest concentration.

These results (Table1 and Table2) show that the placenta in green fruit contained (90.02 % to 71.34%) and in red ones contained 94.24% in “Rouge long” to 62.25% in “Chaabani” of the total amount of capsaicinoids, the seeds (9.75% to 6.26%) in green fruits but in red ones was (9.80% to 2.32%), and the pericarp was (18.91% to 3.72%) and (27.94% to 3.44%) in green and red fruit respectively. These findings support the view that capsaicinoids are synthesized in the placenta and that the presence of capsaicinoids in other parts of the fruit appears to be the result of leakage and diffusion from the placenta to the periderm and seeds (Suzuki et Iwai, 1984; Estrada *et al.*, 2002; Contreras-Padella et Yahia, 1998; Kosukue *et al.*, 2005; Nwokem *et al.*, 2011). Other authors mentioned also Capsaicinoids are accumulated preferentially in the placenta rather than in the pericarp and seeds (Sung *et al.*, 2005; Cisneros-Pineda *et al.*, 2007; Ornelas-Paz *et al.*, 2010).

Fig2: Capsaicinoids content in different parts of green hot pepper varieties

Fig3: Capsaicinoids content in different parts of red hot pepper varieties

Table1: Amount of capsaicinoids in green parts of hot pepper fruits

Amount of capsaicinoids	Varieties			
	RL	Pch	PBK	Ps
Placenta %	81,64	90,02	71,34	85,32
Pericarp %	11,72	3,72	18,91	6,95
seeds %	6,64	6,26	9,75	7,73

Table2: Amount of capsaicinoids in red parts of hot pepper fruits

Amount of capsaicinoides	Varieties			
	RL	Pch	PBK	Ps
Placenta %	94,24	62,25	74,71	86,31
Pericarpe%	3,44	27,94	19,54	7,33
graines%	2,32	9,80	5,75	6,36

CONCLUSION

The results from this study which employed High Performance Liquid Chromatography show at different stage of maturity, that the placenta has the highest concentration of capsaicin in the pepper fruit. Therefore, it is recommended that the epidermal cells of the placenta were the site of capsaicinoids accumulation. The small amount of these alkaloids detected in the pericarp and seeds might be due to the adherence of a small quantity of capsaicinoid coming from the placenta (Estrada *et al.*, 2002).

Differences in capsaicinoids concentration have been reported for different capsicum varieties. Variations in capsaicinoids quantity found in our study could be attributed to intrinsic genetic factors or alternatively to the environmental conditions where they were cultivated. Based on pungency performance, the pungent taste of these varieties can be improved by a genetic cross between the best varieties selected. In this sense the parent with the highest average performance would be useful to produce a better genotype for improved capsaicin content in hot peppers.

REFERENCES

- Antonious G. F., Berke T and Jarret R. L. (2009). Pungency in *Capsicum chinense*. Variation among countries of origin. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health Part B*. 44, 179–184.
- Bosland, P.W. (1992). Chiles: A diverse crop. *HortTechnology* 2(1), 6-10.
- Canto-Flick A., Balam-Uc E., Bello-Bello J. J., Lecona-Guzmán C., Solís-Marroquín D., Avilés-Viñas S., Gómez-Uc E., López-Puc G. and Santana-Buzzy N. (2008). Capsaicinoids Content in Habanero Pepper (*Capsicum chinense* Jacq.): Hottest Known Cultivars. *HortScience* 43 (5), 1344-1349.
- Choi, S.H., Suh, B.S., Kozukue E., Kozukue, N., Levin C.E., Friedman M. (2006). Analysis of the contents of pungent compounds in fresh Korean red peppers and in pepper-containing foods. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 54, 9024- 9031.
- Choux C.I., Foury C.I. (1994). Le piment. In: Productions Légumières-Légumes Fruits, Lavoisier, Paris, pp 271-295.
- Cisneros-Pineda O., Torres-Tapia L.W., Gutiérrez-Pacheco L.C., Contreras- Martín F., González-Estrada T., Peraza-Sánchez S.R. (2007). Capsaicinoids quantification in chili peppers cultivated in state of Yucatan, Mexico. *Food Chemistry* 104, 1755-1760.
- Collins M.D., Mayer-Wasmund L., Bosland P.W. (1995). Improved Method for Quantifying Capsaicinoids in Capsicum using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography. *HortScience* 30, 137-139.
- Constant H. L., Cordell G. A., West D. P., Johnson J. H. (1995). Separation and quantification of capsaicinoids using complexation chromatography. *J. Nat. Prod.* 58, 1925-1928.
- Contreras-Padella M., Yahia E.M. (1998). Changes in capsaicinoids during development maturation and senescence of Chile peppers and relation with peroxidase activity. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 46, 2075-2079.
- De Masi L., Siviero P., Castaldo D., Esposito C., Laratta B. (2007). Agronomic, chemical and genetic profiles of hot peppers (*Capsicum annuum* ssp.). *Molecular Nutrition and Food Research* 51, 1053-1062.
- Estrada B., Bernal M. A., Diaz J., Pomar F., Merino F.(2002). Capsaicinoids in vegetative organs of *Capsicum annuum* L. in relation to fruiting. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 50, 1188-1191.
- Jarret R.L., Baldwin E., Perkins B., Bushway R., Guthrie K.(2007). Diversity of fruit quality characteristics in *Capsicum frutescens*. *HortScience* 42, 16–19.
- Kaale E., Van Schepdael A., Roets E., Hoogmartens J. (2002). Determination of capsaicinoids in topical cream by liquid-liquid extraction and liquid chromatography. *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 30, 1331-1337.
- Kosuge S. and Murata M. (1970). Studies on the pungent principle of Capsicum. Part XIV: chemical constitution of the pungent principle. *Agricultural and Biological Chemistry* 34, 248–256.
- Kozukue N., Han J.S., Kozukue E., Lee S.J., Kim J. A., Lee K.R., Levin C. E. and Friedman M. (2005). Analysis of Eight Capsaicinoids in Peppers and Pepper-Containing Foods by High Performance Liquid Chromatography and Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 53, 9172-9181.

Navarro J.M., Flores P., Garrido C., Martinez V. (2006). Changes in the contents of antioxidant compounds in pepper fruits at different ripening stages, as affected by salinity. *Food Chemistry* 96, 66–73.

Nwokem C.O, Nwokem N.C., Usman Odjobo B.O., Oholi O.J., Yebpella G.G., Batari M. L. (2011). Determination of capsaicin content in various parts of some peppers grown in Nigeria. *Wilolud Journals: Continental Journal Agronomy* 5 (1), 6 – 10.

Ravishankar G.A., Suresh B., Giridhar P., Ramachandra Rao S., Sudhakar Johnson T. (2003). Biotechnological studies on capsicum for metabolites production and plant improvement. *Capsicums*: 97-122.

Sathiamurthy V.A., Veeraragavathatham D., Chezhiyan N. (2002). Studies on the capsaicin content in chilli hybrids. *Capsicum and Eggplant Newsletter* 21, 44-47.

Smith P. G., Villalon B., and Villa P. L. (1987). Horticultural classification of peppers grown in the United States. *HortScience* 22, 11-13.

Surh Y.J., Lee S.S. (1995). Capsaicin, a double-edged sword: toxicity, metabolism, and chemopreventive potential. *Life Sciences* 56, 1845–1855.

Surh Y.J., Seoul S.K. (2002). Antitumor promoting potential of selected spice ingredients with oxidative and anti-inflammatory activities. *Food Chemistry Toxicology* 40, 1091–1097.

Suzuki T., Iwai K. (1984). Constituents of red pepper species: chemistry, biochemistry, pharmacology, and food science of the pungent principle of Capsicum species. In *The alkaloids: Chemistry and pharmacology* Bross, A., Ed.; Academic Press: Orlando, FL, 23, Chapter 4.

Zewdie Y., Bosland P. (2001). Capsaicinoid profiles are not good chemotaxonomic indicators for Capsicum species. *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology* 29, 161–169.

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